

Maximum Sunlight Absorption Using Dual Axis Solar Tracking System

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Abstract— Nowadays, renewable energy has become a primary concern of most countries in the worlds to replace the conventional fossil fuel. Solar energy is the best solution in place to provide electricity. Photovoltaic (PV) panels are the best technology to convert solar energy into electrical energy. Since the Earth is in constant motion, the sunlight absorption is not maximum if we use a fixed solar system. The observation of solar energy will be translated in two forms, the first translation will be oriented for X-axis (Horizontal plan) and the second translation will be at Y-axis (Vertical plan). In this context comes the idea to use a solar tracking system to maximize the efficiency of the photovoltaic panel. In this research, we will present our proposed Dual axis solar tracker system. Hardware results will be shown and we will make a comparative study between the results of our system and other types of sunlight absorbing systems.

Keywords- Dual Axis Solar Tracking, Solar energy, Photovoltaic, Solar Tracking System, Arduino.

I. INTRODUCTION

So far the majority of countries in the world use fossils such as petroleum, natural gas and carbon as the primary source of electricity. This type of energy faces many challenges at the present time, especially with the seriousness of climate changes and the high cost of extraction, shipping and processing. To meet these obstacles and others, countries, factories and individuals are directed towards producing environmentally friendly alternative energy such as solar, wind and geothermal energy.

Of all the renewable energies, we find that solar energy is the most abundant source on the earth, as the energy we receive from the sun in 24 hours can give all world energy needs for one year. To capitalize the solar energy, there are many systems based in photovoltaic technology like fixed panel, single axis tracking and dual axis tracking [1].

In this paper, we firstly show some research methods. Next, we present the principle and types of solar tracking systems. After that, we describe our proposed dual axis solar tracker system. Finally, we present the hardware results and comparative analysis.

II. PREVIOUS STUDIES

In this section, we show a single solar tracking systems and dual axis solar tracking systems.

This study shows the evidence and comparison of improving the single tracking system into a dual axis tracker. The descriptive importance lies on the feasibility of increasing the percent capture efficiency from the sun by the use of the dual tracker. We also try to capitalize the element of time as the sun moves from East to West.

A. Single axis solar tracking systems

Single axis trackers have only one axis of rotation, that means this system has 1 degree of freedom. The panel will move according to north meridian line. This technology can reach efficiency up to 30% if we compare it to fixed panel.

Typical single axis systems will not compensate for real time deflection across the abscissa based on the movement of the sun on a specific day.

- *System based on timer and light sensor*

A single axis solar tracking system has been developed by Mirdanies and al. [2]. A parabolic through concentrated solar power plan system was implemented in this system based on timer to estimate the position of sun after a simple calculation and light sensor (LDR) feedback to correct this estimation [3].

Figure 1. Flowchart how the System works on a computer

The system will move the panel on a half circular track, the initial position start from East with sunrise at 0 degree and final position in west with sun set at 180 degree, as shown in Fig-2 [4].

Figure 2. Assumption of panel movement

This movement is carried out immediately after sunset because with the existing motor speed, it takes a long time to return to the starting position of the sun. The way of the light sensor circuit works is by looking at the difference in the intensity of sunlight received by two light sensors. If the light intensity received by the light sensor $a < b$, the system will order the actuator to move towards the right until $a = b$. If $a > b$, the controller will order the actuator to move towards the left until $a = b$. If the sunlight intensity received by light sensors, a and b is smaller than the minimum light intensity, then the data from this light sensor will not be used [2].

Figure 3. Light sensor simulation

• *System based on relay and light detector*

Another single axis sun tracking system was developed by Ponniran and al. [5]. To trace the position of sun they use LDR light detector. These sensors send information's to microcontroller board as a main processor and two relays as a driver, a DC motor is used to ensure the rotation of the panel [5].

Figure 4. Block diagram of Ponniran and al. system

B. *Dual axis solar tracking systems*

There are many proposed techniques for dual axis solar tracking system. Azimuth and elevation angles are estimated by using astronomical based calculation [4]. This technology can provide 10% to 30% higher efficiency than single axis solar tracking systems and 40% to 60% higher than fixed panel construction [6].

In 2011 a dual axis sun tracking system has been developed by N.Barsoum [7]. The system was based on microcontroller and light sensor. PIC Basic program was written and converted to binary code before being loaded into the tracking controller [7]. After that a light sensor is used to find the position of sun and it sends information to microcontroller then to send order to the motors to move the solar panel to be always normal to the sun.

Figure 5. Basic Software Design Flowchart [8]

III. PRINCIPLE OF SOLAR TRACKING SYSTEMS

To have maximum efficiency, the PV must be normal to the incident wave coming from the sun. But the continuous movement of the sun relative to the Earth does not allow this condition to be achieved. For this, several researchers have worked on this subject in order to obtain a system that follows the path of the sun. We call this system “Solar Tracking System”. Until now there are two types of solar tracking systems:

A. Active trackers

In these trackers, electronic sensors, actuators and control circuit (microcontroller, Arduino, Programmable Logic Controller (PLC)) are used to track the current positions of the sun [9,10].

B. Passive trackers

In these trackers, a volatile liquid compressed in containers is used. This liquid gets evaporated due to solar radiation, so the pressure inside the container will be higher which allows moving the photovoltaic panel in such a way that it always follows the movement of the sun [11].

IV. PROPOSED DUAL AXIS SOLAR TRACKER SYSTEM

In this section, we have developed an active dual axis solar tracker system. The main purpose of this work is to develop our system, measure the output voltage and current, calculate power and efficiency, finally compare the results to fixed PV system and single axis solar tracker system using the same PV panel and same conditions.

A. Materials

Our system is made up of 3 main subsystems.

- Light detection unit: Consists of 4 light dependent resistors (LDR) allowing the light intensity to be measured and converted to analog voltage. These four LDR’s will be grouped two by two in such a way that the first pair will allow to control the movement of the panel to track the sun from East to West and the second pair from North to South. Light dependent resistors are chosen due to its accessibility, low cost and simplicity to use compared to other unit using stainless steel canister [12] or camera [13].

- Monitoring unit: To make this part, Arduino Uno is used as the controller, it’s responsible for all the calculations that our system required, receive and analyses the signal delivered from LDR and finally provides power to the servomotors [16] to rotate panel in each horizontal and vertical directions. Arduino Uno is chosen due to its capability to connect all sensors and it has enough pulse width modulation output pins to support 2 servomotors [14].

- Controlling unit: This unit is used to control the movement of PV panel. To make this, we use two servomotors, how we drive with our Arduino Uno controller. One of this motors follow azimuth sun direction and the other one follow altitude sun direction. We chose servomotors because they have high torque capacity compared to DC motor.

Figure 6. Azimuth and altitude orientation [15]

B. Block diagram of our system

In this part, we will present the different components of our block diagram. We resorted to using 9v rechargeable battery that powers our control unit after that it will be charged by our system, then 4 LDR’s and 2 servo motors to control the movement of the photovoltaic panel, finally will make a charge controller to give the best output voltage for the alimentation of loads and to return feedback voltage to our input.

Figure 7. Block diagram to implement our dual axis solar tracker

C. Flowchart and steps description

- Step 1:** Fix the initial place of the solar panel.
- Step 2:** Microcontroller collects signal from sensors (LDR’s).
- Step 3:** Save this signal in a, b, c and d variables.
 - a: Signal coming from LDR number 4
 - b: Signal coming from LDR number 2
 - c: Signal coming from LDR number 1
 - d: Signal coming from LDR number 3
- Step 4:** Microcontroller calculation
 - $X=a-b$
 - $Y=c-d$

Figure 8. LDR's position

Step 5:

- If $a > b$ then motor number 2 rotates in anti-clock wise direction to move the panel **Left**.
- If $a < b$ then motor number 2 rotates in clock wise direction to move the panel **Right**.
- If $a = b$, motor number 2 will **stop**.

Step 6:

- If $c > d$ then motor number 1 rotates in anti-clock wise direction to move the panel **Down**.
- If $c < d$ then motor number 1 rotates in clock wise direction to move the panel **Up**.
- If $c = d$, motor number 1 will **stop**.

Step 7: End of cycle and return to Step 4.

Figure 9. Flow chart

V. OUTCOMES OF OUR PROPOSED DUAL AXIS SOLAR TRACKER SYSTEM

The readings for static panel, single axis tracker and dual axis tracker are taken in the same day from 8:00am to 5:00pm

for every 1 hour. We use the same type and dimensions of panel. The position of static panel is fixed in such a way that it gives us the best results.

Every hour we measure voltage and current from all systems, after that we calculate power, average power and finally the efficiency.

- $Power(w) = Voltage (v) * Current (I)$
- $Total\ Voltage: V_T = \sum_{i=0}^{10} V_i$
- $Total\ Current: I_T = \sum_{i=0}^{10} I_i$
- $Total\ Power: P_T = \sum_{i=0}^{10} P_i$
- $Average\ Voltage: A_V = \frac{V_T}{10}$
- $Average\ Current: A_I = \frac{I_T}{10}$
- $Average\ Power: A_P = \frac{P_T}{10}$

Note: 10 is the number of hours.

TABLE I. OUTPUT RESULTS OF STATIC PANEL

Static Panel			
TIME (Hr)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Power P _F (W)
8:00	7.12	0.20	1.42
9:00	6.82	0.31	2.11
10:00	6.79	0.40	2.71
11:00	6.86	0.44	3.01
12:00	6.93	0.45	3.11
13:00	7.02	0.41	2.87
14:00	7.00	0.35	2.45
15:00	7.05	0.26	1.83
16:00	6.96	0.15	1.04
17:00	6.71	0.04	0.26
Total	69.26	3.01	20.81
Average	6.92	0.3	2.08

TABLE II. OUTPUT RESULTS OF SINGLE AXIS PANEL

Solar Tracking (Single Axis)			
TIME (Hr)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Power P _s (W)
8:00	6.96	0.26	1.81
9:00	6.82	0.38	2.63
10:00	6.69	0.45	3.04
11:00	6.80	0.46	3.13
12:00	6.76	0.47	3.18
13:00	6.78	0.47	3.19
14:00	7.01	0.43	3.01
15:00	7.01	0.35	2.47
16:00	6.72	0.23	1.6
17:00	6.69	0.12	0.83
Total	68.24	3.62	24.89
Average	6.82	0.36	2.49

TABLE III. OUTPUT RESULTS OF DUAL AXIS PANEL

Solar Tracking (Dual Axis)			
TIME (Hr)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Power P _D (W)
8:00	7.26	0.33	2.4
9:00	6.93	0.44	3.05
10:00	6.84	0.47	3.21
11:00	6.85	0.48	3.29
12:00	6.94	0.48	3.33
13:00	7.04	0.48	3.38
14:00	7.01	0.48	3.36
15:00	7.01	0.46	3.22
16:00	7.06	0.39	2.75
17:00	7.04	0.24	1.69
Total	69.98	4.25	29.68
Average	6.99	0.425	2.97

The above tables show clearly that there is a gradual improvement in power measurements when moving first from the fixed photovoltaic panel to a single axis and then to a dual axis solar tracking system.

Chart 1. Fixed, Single and Dual axis average power comparison

- The Average Power for Fixed panel is: A(PF)= 2.08 W
- The Average Power for Single axis solar tracker is: A(PS)= 2.49 W
- The Average Power for Dual axis solar tracker is: A(PD)= 2.97W
- We can now calculate the efficiency two by two.
- Efficiency between Fixed and Single axis:

$$\eta = \frac{\sum(P_S - P_F)}{\sum P_F} \times 100\%$$

$$\eta = 19.71\%$$
- Efficiency between Single and Dual axis:

- $\eta = \frac{\sum(P_D - P_S)}{\sum P_S} \times 100\%$
- $\eta = 19.27\%$
- Efficiency between Fixed and Dual axis:

$$\eta = \frac{\sum(P_D - P_F)}{\sum P_F} \times 100\%$$

$$\eta = 42.78\%$$

The data plotted from measurements show that the dual axis with 42.78% efficiency is at par more beneficial source of capturing solar energy compared to single axis and fixed axis systems.

Chart 2. Fixed, Single and Dual axis average power comparison

VI. CONCLUSION

In this research, we have made a descriptive study of the different models of sun tracking systems. After that, we built our own dual axis tracking system, based in Arduino Uno as a controller. And then our system absorbed the solar energy as much as possible and increases the efficiency. We made measurements on 3 different systems, we started with a fixed system, then with single axis solar tracker and finally with dual axis solar tracker. Analyses of the results obtained, it showed us that our dual axis tracking system gives us the best results which generated 42.78% more power than fixed panel and 19.71% more than single axis tracker. This indicates the importance of research and development in this area, as the increase in energy can exceed 60% especially with the constant development of solar energy panels.

So, it can be said that the dual axis solar tracker is able to contribute to solving part of the economic and environmental problems. And this method can be adopted for further development to be an alternative solution in the near future to get rid of all harmful energy sources.

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